

The Relationship of Succession Planning and Glass Ceiling with Talent Management in Textile Sector of Pakistan

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Abstract

To survive and grow in today's fast-paced business environment, competitive businesses must adapt to new strategies in a variety of fields. 'Talent management, which has risen in prominence in recent years, can be used to find qualified candidates for specific positions. It includes the value and requirements of skilled employees' organization, as well as the concept of employee roles, gender, attitudes, and efficient succession within companies. Because of the increasing number of women in management roles, the concept of the glass ceiling effect has regained huge popularity recently. Whereas succession planning is the process or strategy for transferring leadership from one person to another. The glass ceiling effect, on the other hand, is regarded as a firm barrier that prevents women from being promoted to executive positions in management. Both of these aspects are critical for talent management in the modern era, and they must be taken into account when recruiting and retaining talented individuals in businesses, regardless of gender. This highlights the importance of identifying company succession planning strategies as well as the glass ceiling for women in organizations to identify their efforts toward effective talent management for maximum organizational success. Furthermore, while many organizational leaders are eager to implement cutting-edge talent management programs as soon as possible, it is necessary to identify the most critical variables in the implementation of such a program.

Keywords: Succession Planning, Glass Ceiling, Talent Management, Textile Sector

Introduction

Businesses, the environment, and competitive enterprises must adapt to changes in strategy in a variety of fields to survive and maintain their development in the incredibly fast-paced world. Talent management, which has become more important in recent years, can be used to find the right people for the right job. Rapid changes in globalization, technology, and demographics have had significant effects on work and organizations around the world. These changes are also upsetting long-standing talent management concerns. The progressive companies around the globe are now realizing their weak talent management practices as they are unable to meet the needs of their

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workers and eventually the overall performance of companies is declining (Collings, Mellahi, and Cascio 2019), As a result, a new breed of modern talent management practitioners is refocusing their efforts on identifying the significant factors that can improve or degrade their talent management practices.

Because of Pakistan's current economic and competitive challenges, management must be more attentive than ever before to ways to improve worker performance. By considering the recruiting and selection process, as well as succession planning, as different dimensions of any enterprise, talented employees become resources for the organizations, resulting in a competitive advantage, long-term viability, and growth through the optimal use of their talent resources.

There are 464 textile mills in Pakistan, with 5% listed on the Pakistan Stock Exchange (PSX) (Pakistan Stock Exchange Limited). Pakistan is looking at global markets with poor talent management. However, due to the large number of textile mills in Pakistan, there are structural, cultural, behavioral, and environmental factors that could strongly impact the effective implementation of talent management strategies. When talent is filtered through various challenges/barriers, it has been discovered that talent management strategies result in talent misuse. The overall performance of the organization suffers as a result of how people either do not want to stay with the organization or do not perform properly. According to other studies, the more skilled people believe talent management is effective, the more they commit to improving their leadership skills.

As a result, a lot of interest has been devoted to the concept of talent management among companies, with various companies adopting myriad strategies or philosophies for the management (TM) is described to be the processes or activities involving systematic identification, attraction, engagement, retention, development, and deployment of particular talents of companies that are valuable for the organization for creating the strategic sustainable success (Gallardo-Gallardo, Thunnissen, and Scullion, 2020). Today, the unprecedented business contexts complexity in terms of technology, globalization, and border changes related to geopolitical, socio-economic, and demographic concerns, recruiting, retaining, and developing the talent for navigating the challenges faced by companies in the modern era (Reiche Lee, and Allen, 2019).

It covers the value and necessity of talented employees in organizations, as well as the concept of employee roles, gender perspectives, and effective succession within organizations. Because of the increasing number of women in management positions, the concept of the glass ceiling effect has resurfaced. Succession planning, also recognized as replacement planning, is the process or strategy for passing leadership from one person to another (Oduwusi, 2018). On the other hand, the glass ceiling effect is described to be the social barrier that prevents women in organizations to be promoted to executive posts in management (Ronnie and Glasiter, 2020). Both of these concepts are crucial for talent management in the modern era, and they must be taken seriously to attract and retain talented employees in organizations, regardless of gender.

Thus, there is a need for answers to practitioners' practical TM questions.

When employees do not engage in stereotyped behavior with one another, succession planning will be successful. Continuity planning or talent management in the organization must include succession planning; however, many organizations overlook this area. For example, a recent survey of HR executives from more than 100 companies found that 44% of companies have no succession plan and 70% of companies can improve their succession plans.

The 'Glass Ceiling' effect refers to the widespread resistance to women and minorities reaching top management positions in major corporations. When women had children, it was assumed that they

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would take a significant amount of time off or leave the workforce entirely. Yet, in both developed and developing economies, the link between talent management and untapped female potential is under studied. Surprisingly, no link between gender quotes and talent management been found in the literature. More flexibility needed than ever by both individuals and organizations, and we have the resources to satisfy these demands. One issue that has emerged in Pakistan as result of several preconceptions is known as the "Glass Ceiling." Succession planning becomes a problem when skill and resources are in short supply.

The study's goal is to lay the groundwork for developing research questions and identifying a foundation for the investigation. As a result, the current study's research questions are: What is the relationship between succession planning and Talent management? What is the relationship between Glass Ceiling and Talent management?

The objective of this research is to figure out what factors influence talent management in businesses. The following sub-objectives of the current study will be considered in light of the role of specific factors: To examine the relationship between Succession Planning and Talent Management. To examine the relationship between Glass Ceiling and Talent Management. The research questions will lead to the formation of a research hypothesis, which will identify the assumptions that must be evaluated further. As a result, the current study's presumed assumptions will be followed, which will lead to the testing methods: Succession Planning significante and positivity impacts Talent Management? Does glass Ceiling negatively impact Talent Management?

Talent management is becoming increasingly important to businesses worldwide as a way to get a competitive edge in the marketplace and to make the most use of human capital resources for sustained organisational success. Examining the variables that could affect talent management companies is crucial in this context. The glass ceiling for women and succession planning are thus the two most recent issues affecting organisational performance.

The role of succession planning and the glass ceiling for women in talent management organisations have not yet been addressed in a single research, despite the fact that both topics have been examined independently in a variety of settings.

The importance of succession planning for a company's long-term performance and the effectiveness of its personnel management strategy highlights the necessity for the current study. By identifying key factors that influence the level of talent management in firms, the underlying study will advance our understanding of talent management. Academics and managers can benefit from the glass ceiling research by learning more about women's roles in the workplace and the obstacles faced by women in developing nations. Women in developing nations will be able to comprehend the value of succession planning as a means of enhancing talent management inside organizations to foster creativity and innovation.

The research will also demonstrate how big businesses have addressed the glass ceiling effect and long-term succession planning strategies, emphasizing the significance of the chosen factors for an organizational succession. Governmental organizations will also acknowledge the obstacles to advancement that women face in the workplace, enabling the government to develop and execute efficient laws concerning women's rights in the workplace.

Literature Review

In the modern era, organizations face the huge challenge of provision of component managers

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because of the deepening of competition and expansion of challenges. Thus, accurate planning of talents by the organizations as well as capacity building to assume positions of management is the major agenda being focused on recently by the organizations. The importance of succession planning, in this regard, has been clearly understood by organizations in terms of continuous and dynamic process. The recent highly competitive world demands that organizations must achieve a talented workforce and their vision must go beyond the replacement of the workforce, thus exerting the impact of succession planning on talent management (Philips, 2020).

As described earlier, success planning replaces the talents in the organization with Top management positions or executive posts. Thus, considered the credible, systematic, and modern approach used by organizations, for the identification of talents as well as empowerment of human capital in cases where intermediate or senior executives in the Key positions of companies and on the verge of retirement, actually and then leave the organization due to any reason (Toushan and Masri, 2020). Hence, according to Owolabi and Adeosun, (2021). Succession planning is used as an effective tool by organizations for identifying and promoting human talent. Moreover, the organizations are well aware of complex processes to identify the talented forces and capital for succession as well as empowering them to key positions, actually plan to manage such talent, leading to talent management being highly influenced by succession planning programs of organizations (Sohel-Uz-Zaman, 2018).

Moreover (Zafar and Akhtar, 2020) stated the process of succession planning involves the transmission of power and status, occurring from one person to the next, and often look inside the organizations to identify and attract the next generation of leaders. It is further reported by Black et al. (2019) that effective succession planning is cost-effective and is done to ensure three important aspects;

- (a) The qualified individuals assume the position of leadership.
- (b) Adequate preparation is held by companies' unexpected events.
- (c) There exists the appropriate health care perianal mix in organizations for functioning.

It appears that an immense challenge is posed by succession planning for organizations as they tend to tangle with problems continuously concerning the provision of critical on the job experiences to employees, the depletion of resources for the development of employees as well as rapid aging of the workforce, ultimately creating shortfalls for the experienced managerial talent for the positions of senior management or leadership (Murimi and Muniuri, 2018) Moreover, the workforce statistics of US also exert that an incredible challenge is posed by succession planning because of the retiring of the baby boomer generation and college-educated workers are prepared to replace the experienced personal (USGS, 2019). Additionally, a recent article in the journal of Management development articulates that the particular challenges of career development are faced by women or people of color or people of color in the corporate environment, for instance, the lack of personal networkers and mentors, stereotype behaviors, the lack of challenges or visible assignments (Van den Bergh and Du Plessis, 2021). Thus, succession planning is considered to be an important aspect of talent management in organizations.

In Leadership positions, females have long been underrepresented disproportionately. This highlights the concept of the glass ceiling whereby women face barriers in promoting to leadership positions. The phenomenon evolved in the 1980s and is analog to the concept of a 'Good old boys club'. It is revealed by previous research that gender discrimination is the major factor linked to unequal treatment of women within organizations or in the workplace. Although in the 21st century, women have significantly progressed across private and public sectors, there still exists a leadership

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gap (Salvai and Kuschel, 2020).

The Office of Personnel Management (OPM) is responsible for the federal employees' overall personal management and it states that for decades, in leadership positions, women have been significantly underrepresented (Nelson and Piatak, 2021). Although a 3.42% increase in the advancement of women to leadership positions has been reported, its growth is observed to be inconsistent across various companies.

The phenomenon of the Glass ceiling can be investigated in various manifestations or constructs, for instance, world commitment, workplace environment, wage gap or other societal or cultural factors (Bullard and Wright, 2018). The managers in certain organizations consider women to be less dedicated and less committed to their job or position at the workplace because of having family obligations. Various other studies have reported gender differences in the roles of leadership (Guvenen, Kaplan, and Song, 2020). Comparing men and women in organizations or workplaces, the degradation in the compensation for women is restored and it is unable to be explained completely based on differences in work history, career interruptions, qualifications, or work experiences (Kapoor, Sardana, and Sharma, 2021). Moreover, more isolation and higher stress are felt by women executives compared to male counterparts in the workplace and therefore, the glass ceiling appears in organizations. Such pressures manifest themselves in various issues, like reduced self-confidence and increased inferiority complex within society has organizations. Accordingly, according to (Bhatnagar and Mathur, 2015), the slow advancement for women is attributed to four factors:

- Less acknowledgment and appreciation are received by women managers compared to men.
- The discrepancy in the training of men and women.
- Risky jobs are seldom opted for by women.
- Women are not highly supported by their families related to jobs.

Since the last decade, the agendas of various countries' social and public organizations are giving priority to the talent management of women. Women are part of half of the active workforce in the organizations; nevertheless, this representation is unable to be replaced in director-level positions or top management globally, like in Latin American companies (PwC, 2016; Zehnder, 2016).

Consequently, reduced growth potential is reported for the countries and companies that are unable to take advantage of their women's talents as well as the education of both men and women. To prevent the loss of female talent in organizations as well as the collaboration of this issue with economic and social development, effective policies and practices or senior management (Spencer, Blazek, and Orr, 2019). One of such decisions in Norway was particularly disruptive. Norway introduced the quota of 40% of participation of females on boards of directors in municipal, co-operative societies and publicly traded companies (Sweigart, 2012). Although there was increasing opposition, still the consequences of such a law were quite positive. It was further confirmed that in Norway, the democratization of boards of directors has ultimately improved the decision-making and boards' collective intelligence as well as the effective governing culture of board management. It also resulted in reduced risks and prevention of group thinking effects. The most significant results were reported in the form of exploitation and search of talented women for their contribution to different networks of business, beyond conventional corporate power networks.

Zehnder (2016) further reported that in most countries (IPSA or by size Top 100), the proportion of women in board positions is very low. The ratio of women's representation is only reported to be 8% in 2019, increasing from 6.4% in 2018. The author further revealed that such companies adopt the strategy of 'tokenism', referring to the practice and policy of making superficial gestures

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regarding the inclusion of minority or underprivileged groups members. Accordingly, the effort regarding the inclusion of women on board intends to create gender diversity, ultimately deflecting discrimination accusations (Robert and Brown, 2019). Therefore glass ceiling for women is still increasing and that affects the glass ceiling women, such as the stereotyping behaviors of employees in the workplace. It indicates the invariant and repetitive behaviors patterns of employees without spreading rumors about women's role in management positions, leading to negative spreading rumors about women's role in the management positions, leading to a negative impression of the ultimate objective of removing the glass ceiling for women in organizations. Hence, the Talent management for women in organizations will also be highly influenced by such activity.

Theoretical Model

In above figure 1 research model shows that, the above research model was developed. We have two independent variables in this model: succession planning and glass ceilings. We see in this study that these two variables have a significant relationship with a dependent variable which is talent management.

Research Design

The underlying study will be explanatory as it intends to explore the contribution of succession planning and the glass ceiling for women in the talent management within the organization. The study will also explore the implementation of talent management techniques in the organization and thus, the primary study will eventually explore the relationship among variables from the core. For the respective purpose, the study will explore the relationship using a questionnaires survey and thus, Quantitative studies using survey techniques will be conducted.

The study further intends to work on objective data, based on numbers and realistic information provided by data, instead of subjective data. This entails the concept of research philosophy. The research philosophy describes the analysis (Hirlimann, 2018). The current study will focus on the concept of “Theory of knowledge”, considering what is known to be a true concept, and will rely on Interpretivism research philosophy, considering that the social world can be described subjectively.

Thus, a researcher in the respective research tends to play an effective role as per his interests and also explains the particular phenomenon according to findings.

The underlying study intends to research the Textile sector of Pakistan. The population of the study includes all the Textile companies working in Pakistan. However, it is not possible to collect Data from textile companies separately, and therefore, the sample is selected for the researchers that represent the entire population. The selected textile companies will be those which are within

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The current research intends to study the non-quantifiable variables and the most effective technique to collect data for the respective variables is through a questionnaires survey (Mertens, 2018). Therefore, the current study will collect data using a questionnaire's survey and the survey will be disturbed physically to respondents. Total sample size was 230 in which we receive 170 respondents. physical The respondents of the study will be executives involved in succession planning, managers involved in implementing talent management and dealing with the glass ceiling for women.

The performed data using questionnaires will be compiled in SPSS and then the analysis will be performed in SPSS. The statistical analysis will include the descriptive analysis of the data, the correlation and regression analysis to identify the correlation among variables, the impact of succession planning, and the glass ceiling for women. The respective statistical analysis will effectively explore how talent management is impacted by various factors.

The current study will effectively utilize only the resources of the personnel working in the textile companies as well as the personnel who will conduct a questionnaire survey by physically visiting the Textile mills. Moreover universities lab will also be used as an effective resource for using the SPSS software to perform the analysis.

Results

The focus of this chapter is on data analysis. Firstly, A four-question demographics analysis has been performed. Descriptive statistics were used to provide basic information about variables as well as to highlight the relationship between variables. The statistics of the relationship between computed variables were visualized using correlation analysis. Regression analysis is the method for determining which variables have an impact on a particular topic.

Demographic is defining a theory of human size, structure, and sampling development and the analysis of the record of the beginning and ending of the human for example death, birth, migration, etc. The demographical factor is a very important factor used to testify to the hypothesis result. Its involved gender, age, occupation, and qualification according to sample questionnaires.

Table 1

		Gender			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	108	63.5	63.5	63.5
	Female	62	36.5	36.5	100.0
	Total	170	100.0	100.0	

Table 1 shows the total number of male participants is 108 and females participant are 62 total respondents are 170 the result outcome is that out of 170 participants, 63.4% were male females based on our sample the gender equality among the employee's performance in the firms is not equally the same for both male and female.

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Table2:

		Age			Cumulative
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent
Valid	20-30	60	35.3	35.3	35.3
	30-40	67	39.4	39.4	74.7
	40-50	27	15.9	15.9	90.6
	Above 50	16	9.4	9.4	100.0
	Total	170	100.0	100.0	

Table 2 shows the distribution of the respondent's age the total number of respondents is 170 Of which 60 (35.3%) belong to the age category of 21-30. From the age of 31-40 participants are 67 (39.4%) which is relatively more than those 21-30 age of the participants. About 27 (15.9%) of the respondents are aged 41-50 and another interesting point is that 16 (9.4%) represent the age above 50. This shows that respondents came from a wide range which belongs to mature ages.

Table 3 shows the educational level of the participant the total number of respondents is 170 the result describes that out of 170 participants 28.8% are holders of a bachelor's degree 51.2% are master's degree 18.2% are holders of an M. Phil degree 1.8% are the holders of Ph.D. The bachelor's degree participants are 31. The Ph.D. degree participants are 3. Our research result shows that Masters's degree participants are comparatively more than the other participant in the educational level.

3:

		Qualification			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative
					Percent
Valid	Bachelors	49	28.8	28.8	28.8
	Masters	87	51.2	51.2	80.0
	MPhil	31	18.2	18.2	98.2
	PhD	3	1.8	1.8	100.0
	Total	170	100.0	100.0	

Table 4:

		Occupation			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative
					Percent
Valid	Top-level management	55	32.4	32.4	32.4
	Middle-level management	51	30.0	30.0	62.4
	Executive	30	17.6	17.6	80.0
	Non managerial	34	20.0	20.0	100.0
	Total	170	100.0	100.0	

Table 4 shows the designation or position of the employee within the firm therefore we also include this category in our study. The total number of respondents was 170. The result shows that out of the participants, 32.4% are employees in top-level management, 30.0% are employed in middle-level management, 17.6% are employed as an executive, and 20.0% are employed as a non,

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managerial.

Table 5 Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Talent management	17.1176	3.03398	170
Succession planning	14.0882	1.81329	170
Glass ceiling	20.8000	3.06845	170

This table 5 shows the descriptive statistics. The mean of Talent management was found to be 17.1176 and its standard deviation is 3.03398. The man of succession planning was found to be 14.0882 and its standard deviation is 1.81329. The man of the glass ceiling is found to be 20,8000 and its standard deviation is 3.06845.

Table 6 Correlations

		Correlations		
		Talent management	Succession planning	Glass ceiling
Talent management	Pearson Correlation	1	.305**	.256**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.001
	N	170	170	170
Succession planning	Pearson Correlation	.305**	1	.185*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.016
	N	170	170	170
Glass ceiling	Pearson Correlation	.256**	.185*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.016	
	N	170	170	170

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The correlation between variables is shown in the table 6 above. The relationship between variables in the study was examined using the analysis of the variables. Although talent management is a dependent variable, succession planning and the glass ceiling are both independent variables. The relationship between talent management and succession planning is positively correlated with each other (r=.305). Likewise, the relationship glass ceiling is also positive (r=.185). However, the relationship is glass ceiling is weaker than talent management.

Model Summary

Model	R	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics			Sig. F Change		
				R Square	F	df1		df2	
1	.366 ^a	.134	.123	2.84047	.134	12.905	2	167	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), glass ceiling, succession planning

In the table above, R2 indicates variations in the data. The linear relationship of succession planning, glass ceiling, and talent management explains the 13%. To put it another way, we can say that 13 is the number of independent variables. In addition, the adjusted r², which refers to

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sample estimates of population co-efficient determinations adjusted for the degree of freedom, is 12.3%. Deviations around the regression line are 2.84, according to the standard error of estimates.

Table 8

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	208.247	2	104.124	12.905	.000 ^b
	Residual	1347.400	167	8.068		
	Total	1555.647	169			

a. Dependent Variable: talent management

b. Predictors: (Constant), glass ceiling, succession planning

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		95.0% Confidence Interval for B		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	6.595	2.083		3.166	.002	2.483	10.708
	succession planning	.446	.123	.266	3.636	.000	.204	.688
	glass ceiling	.204	.072	.206	2.814	.005	.061	.347

a. Dependent Variable: talent management

We accept all hypotheses because the p-value in the ANOVA table is .000, which is less than 0.05, and we conclude that the overall model of this study is highly significant.

Table 9 Coefficients

The average of the employees when there are no problems is equal to 6.595. The value of b in succession planning indicates that if one unit of succession planning is increased, talent management will change 44.6 times. The value of the glass ceiling will decrease by 20.4% if one unit is added to talent management.

Discussion and conclusions

A population sample size of a study is 230 has been used. The questionnaires were sent to top-level managers, executives, and middle-level managers in the textile industry. SPSS software was used to analyse the data collected from the participant. In this study number of male participants are higher than female. The majority of the participants were between the ages of 30 and 40 years. Furthermore, talent management practices are in the process in Pakistani organizational culture, but not at a substantial stage, which is required to cultivate employee personalities so that they can use or optimize their skills for the respective sector. The discussion is leading to an acceptance of the critical role that organizational culture plays in overall talent management processes. Because of the shortfall of talented employees in the current business environment, talent management is critical for organizations. Although talent management is often associated with several other practices, scholars have expanded the scope of human resource activities by associating talent management with a variety of other practices to give it a more flexible approach. Organizational culture is linked to the organization's core values and belief system. The development of

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organizational culture is the responsibility of leaders. The daily activities of the employees in the organization reflect the organizational culture. In the organization, there are various kinds of cultures, such as entrepreneurial and marketing. The type of organizational culture present in the organization has an impact on the organization's management practices. To gain a competitive advantage, it is well understood that aligning organizational culture with business strategy is crucial.

This research found that stereotype behaviour has an impact on succession planning and talent management in Pakistan's textile industry. Employee appearance, attitudes, and behaviour can also contribute to stereotyping behaviour, which can be both positive and negative.

The study shed light on the relationship between succession planning and the glass ceiling with talent management in Pakistan textile industries. Although talent management practices are being implemented in the Pakistani sector, there are very few industries that are not providing employees with what they are truly worth. In our research, we look at succession planning and talent management, both of which play a significant role in ensuring that the best candidate for a job is found. Employees may fail to achieve the deserving position for a variety of reasons, such as biases or rating errors.

The retention of talented employees is a critical component of a company's entire talent management strategy, which is defined as the development of employees of enhanced systems for attracting, developing, retaining, and deploying individuals with the necessary skills and aptitude to fulfil current and future business requirements. Employees leave, according to a recent study for a variety of reasons, including higher pay or improved career prospects. Job inclination, high attrition, and productivity and professional development are all concerns the Human Resource community and have a direct impact on business in an industry that is becoming increasingly people-intensive. In such a situation, it is essential to identify the factors that influence talent management practices. Organizations can reduce employee intentions to leave the organization and many of the negative outcomes and costs by employing talent management practices.

There are several practices for succession planning, but almost they all share a common thread. Some presume it is a succession planning and selection process for the future senior management team. It is an adequate pool of suitable talents for in-house recruitment for other groups. Some succession planning is a "future-proof" strategy that helps the holder to grow and perform successfully in the future. There is a common thread running through all three explanations: "having the right people in the right jobs at the right time". Investing in human resources necessitates careful planning. Succession planning is an important organizational business strategy for developing and retaining talent under talent management.

Organizations are faced with social changes such as globalization and technological advancements daily and increased global cutthroat competition in the current scenario. Companies must be able to anticipate technological advancements and compete globally. Apart from economic changes, demographic shifts are also putting pressure on businesses. The active population of today's society is rapidly aging, while fewer young individuals are entering the workforce. Furthermore, the so-called "baby boom" generation of workers is gradually retiring. These changes not only result in a labor shortage but also put the organization at risk of losing knowledgeable and experienced young people. Even though talent management is critical to any organization's success, the most critical labour-management concern is retaining skilled and youthful people shortly. In the war for talent, organizational success is dependent on efficient recruiting and retention. Human resources can assist in achieving this goal by focusing on five main areas: organizational stability, stressing

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employer brand and reputation, building integrated talent strategies, enabling multilevel accountability, participating in talent management efforts, and offering chances for professional and personal development.

Implications

All organizations globally need employees that possess the necessary knowledge, skills, abilities, behavior, and connections to accomplish business goals (Morgan and Jardin, 2010). Even though talent management has a long history in Pakistan's textile industries, the industry is unsure of which specific talent management models to use. To reach the crucial objective of successful talent management, managers and staff in the HR department as well as other employees and managers should gain a deeper understanding of talent management and make it a key strategic goal for their organizations.

- Managers in every area within a company, regardless of rank, should value talent and make an effort to nurture and develop it for pivotal roles in the future. When one of these important workers departs the company for personal reasons or better employment possibilities, they should also react favorably.

- In order to succeed in talent management more fully, they need to introduce additional talent management programs within their companies. It implies that in addition to strengthening their development programs, companies should focus on additional projects like luring, developing, and keeping talent as well as making an effort to prevent talent misuse.

Limitations and future research

Every researcher has their own set of constraints. This one is no exception, and it has some limitations that will be discussed further down. Due to the challenges of gathering data from the textile industry, the majority of them are hesitant to participate in this study.

Data from sufficient populations could not be obtained, and purposive sampling was employed. The study's findings cannot be applied to a larger population. Other researchers should conduct additional research on this topic in order to provide more results from larger samples using random sampling techniques.

This study first examined the connection between succession planning and the textile industry's "glass ceiling" in Pakistan. Without a doubt, there are additional independent factors that have a big influence on talent management. Future study in Pakistan's textile industries should thus incorporate more talent management prediction factors.

Second, given that this study shows that talent management is being employed more often in the textile, IT, and financial sectors, future researchers should stratify organisations according to their sizes and industries before choosing the sample. All organisations globally need employees that possess the necessary knowledge, skills, abilities, behaviour, and connections to accomplish business goals (Morgan and Jardin, 2010).

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